

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

INSTITUTE OF ALLIED HEALTH SCIENCES

PROCEEDINGS OF THE MEETING OF BOARD OF STUDIES HELD ON 05.03.2022 AT 9:30 AM IN THE BOARD ROOM

Members present:

1. Prof. Devaseelan S	Chairman,
2. Mr. Naveen Bappanadu	Member
3. Mrs. Swathi D	Member
4. Ms. Varsha A C	Member
5. Ms. Kavya Shettigar K	Member
6. Mrs. Swathi Krishnan	Member
7. Ms. Brilly Anto	Member
8. Mrs. Priyadhersini. S	Member
9. Ms. Maureen Edwards	Member
10. Dr. Vrinda J Bhat	External Member
11. Dr. David Rosario	External Member
12. B Balaji Narayan	Industrial Expert

The BOS discussed the following agenda:

1. Approve the minutes of the last Meeting of the BOS held on 20.10.2021.
2. NEP based Syllabus Revise
3. Revision on Credit Based System
4. Syllabus of M.Sc. Courses Revise
5. Discussion regarding the Value-Added Course.
6. Formation of Board of Examination

Agenda No. 1: Confirmations of the minutes of Last Meeting of Board of Studies which was held on 20.10.2021. The Resolution was taken as per the suggestions of the BOS Members in the last meeting, all the Allied Health Sciences Courses were asked to update the changes proposed by the BOS Members.

Agenda No. 2: The Syllabus was reviewed as per the NEP 2021 in the last meeting. Hence it was reviewed. The suggestion was approved by the BOS and all the courses were asked to update the syllabus as proposed by the Chairman.

Agenda No. 3: As the Syllabus must be updated based on the NEP 2021, the credit allocation for the subjects must be changed accordingly. It was suggested to follow the new credit-based system for every courses and resolution was taken accordingly, updates and changes were approved as proposed by the BOS.

Agenda No. 4: It was suggested that all the syllabus of the M.Sc. courses to be updated as per the current standards by the BOS, the resolution was taken accordingly, and changes were approved as proposed by the BOS.

Agenda No. 5: As per the suggestion of the BOS regarding the Value-Added Courses, Department of Medical Imaging Technology suggested a course, “Patient Care Radiation Safety”, The Department of Cardiac Care Technology and Cardiac Vascular Technology suggested a course, “BLS & ACLS Training” and Department of Optometry suggested a course, “Spectacle Manufacturing procedure for Optometrist”. The resolution was taken accordingly for the Academic Year 2022 regarding the Value-Added courses and the same was approved by the BOS.

Agenda No. 6: The Chairperson explained the criteria related to the selection of the BOE members and requested to suggest the eligible staff names. The resolution was taken accordingly, and the Board prepared the list of BOE members for the Academic year 2021-2022. Changes were approved as proposed by the BOS.

The meeting was concluded at 11:30 AM with a vote of thanks by Ms. Kavya Shettigar K, Member of Board of Studies.

Prof. Devaseelan S,
Chairman,
BOS in Allied Health Science

Members present:

Prof. Devaseelan S

Mr. Naveen Bappanadu

Mrs. Swathi D

Ms. Varsha A C

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